

Footprint-Optimized Orchestration and Management of Secure Complex Services over 6G Continuum

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Abstract—This paper presents a security orchestration framework driven by bio-inspired and energy efficiency paradigms and embedded in the security architecture currently being developed in the NETWORK project. This project also entails the design and implementation of different security enablers that are essential for providing efficient and ubiquitous security management in future 6G networks. We delineate the relevant components and the framework and delve into their operation via two selected use cases. We also discuss the key challenges and future research crucial to enable the integration of smart and net-zero security orchestration in 6G networks.

Index Terms—Security management, orchestration, net-zero mechanisms, 6G networks

I. INTRODUCTION

6G will be a highly distributed computing and connectivity architecture. With the advances in softwarisation, it is expected that most of the software of a 6G system will be cloud-based [1]. Moreover, energy consumption is expected to increase substantially with the increasing number of connected devices and data-intensive applications in 6G edge-to-cloud networks. At the same time, the number of threat actors and vulnerabilities is growing. Security is not optional in 6G, and existing solutions are energy-intensive. Finding sustainable and efficient energy solutions to power these networks while ensuring security-/trust-/sustainability- compliant provision of cloud-native services will be a significant challenge. Efficient optimization techniques (including scalable AI) can be used to improve the network-user sustainability (in terms of energy efficiency and trust-compliance), by predicting and dynamically adapting to changes in traffic-workload patterns, user demand, and environmental conditions.

This paper describes a footprint-optimized orchestration and management framework exploiting bio-inspired and energy efficiency paradigms and being developed in the NETWORK project [2]. This project deals with innovations in the secure complex 6G services over the continuum, including secure-by-design federated slice orchestration and management and enhanced payload mobility. The NETWORK Footprint-Optimized Management and Orchestration (NAFOMO) is designed to address the following objectives:

- 1) to integrate an AI approach for ensuring Secure-by-design federated slice orchestration and management,
- 2) to provide offloading of specific security services, microservices, and network functions as pure data plane programmable pipelines,
- 3) to develop a composition overlay of microservices and optimization algorithms that tackle the trade-off between security and energy consumption,
- 4) to elaborate on a computing continuum sustainable security, fostering platform-agnostic payload placement and controlled/optimized placement of security-related CPU instructions,

To this end, we provide a blueprint of key technologies and how they can be integrated into a framework for footprint-optimized orchestration and management of secure complex services over the 6G continuum in this work. The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section II describes the technical background for provisioning energy-efficient security orchestration in future networks. Section III describes the NAFOMO developed in the NETWORK project. Section IV elaborates on the relevant use cases for the NAFOMO. Finally, we conclude

with some discussion and future work in Section V.

II. TECHNICAL BACKGROUND FOR 6G SERVICES AND ORCHESTRATION FOR SECURITY

Emerging propositions of the 6G architecture promote - among others - the cloudification of 6G services, distribution across the edge-to-cloud continuum, and the integration of AI-based decision support [1]. This, combined with the pressing need for supporting sustainable networks, makes it critical to develop secure-by-design orchestration and management of 6G slices.

A. Energy-aware secure-by-design orchestration

Energy efficiency is a critical factor in enabling the sustainable operation of 6G services and the underlying infrastructure. Tackling energy-exhausting threats in 6G is a non-trivial challenge. Since the emergence of cloudification in 5G, attacks against cloud infrastructure have increased, especially, (Distributed) Denial of Service (DoS/DDoS) and, more recently, the evolved Denial of Sustainability (DoSt) - a.k.a Economic Denial of Sustainability (EDoS) - variant [3]–[5]. Both forms of attacks exploit the cloud capacity to absorb growth in workload by scaling up virtual resources and the primitive decision support from threat shielding systems to the orchestration counterparts. The additional challenge with DoSt attacks is the difficulty in detecting them. Unlike DoS/DDoS attacks, DoSt does not disable its target service. Instead, it increases the load/demand level to a threshold below the capacity limit, thus continually exhausting service resources and causing them to scale up, leading to inflated costs for the service provider [1], [6]. For cloudified services, this translates into higher operational costs for the service provider, incurred by the additional cloud cost to absorb the attack, rendering the service unsustainable to operate [3]–[5], [7]. The impact of DoSt can be particularly high for resource-intensive services, such as AI and Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLTs), as a slight increase in demand could result in a significant increase in resource utilization. Added to that, the novel ways in which such services can be abused - for example, through ‘convergence prevention’, makes attack tracing and identification hard [6].

Reciprocally, the stringent requirements for 6G QoS, require ultra-fast responsiveness and reliability from cybersecurity services, in addition to being energy efficient. These, namely energy efficiency, responsiveness, and reliability, may well be some of the biggest challenges to be addressed for 6G cybersecurity services [1], [8]–[10].

To enable cloudified, energy-efficient, and sustainable 6G networks at scale, it is essential to develop scalable cybersecurity solutions that incorporate threat intelligence for DoS/DDoS and DoSt attacks into the orchestration middleware. In addition, advanced anomaly detection methods should be created for emerging services like AI and DLT, enhancing the middleware with logic and intelligence to inform orchestration decisions. These decisions may include service placement, migration, routing, and mapping based on the

infrastructure’s security robustness and the demand patterns of 6G services. Moreover, the trajectory of requirements’ rigor strongly suggests increased reliance on proactive decision-making based on continual learning and predictions to achieve the high responsiveness needed to meet said requirements.

B. AI for Orchestration and Defense

AI for Orchestration and Defense in the NAFOMO context focuses on leveraging advanced machine learning techniques to autonomously manage, secure, and optimize network resources, ensuring resilient defense mechanisms against emerging cyber threats while maintaining seamless service orchestration. In order to achieve this on the 6G network, a threat & attack detection function is placed on the Core Network/Edge Network that continuously monitors the traffic between the Radio Access Network (RAN) and the Core Network (N3 interface gNB-UPF or N6 interface UPD-DN). Based on the threats or attacks detected on the network, AI models appropriately determine network slices and move clients to slices according to their behavior. Specifically for the identified malicious users, the orchestrator moves them to a low-priority low bandwidth slice or even disconnects them from the network. This is realized using O-RAN compatible implementation of Radio Intelligent Controllers (RIC) to enforce decisions to the RAN.

C. Data plane computation offloading

One key area of focus for more efficient resource utilization in 6G is the data plane, where user data is processed, routed, and forwarded across the network. Data plane computation offloading refers to the process of moving compute-intensive tasks away from centralized processing units to distributed edge or network nodes closer to the user. This offloading shifts the computational burden from a central cloud or core network to various points within the network’s infrastructure.

This results in several key advantages. First, reduced latency is achieved by offloading computation tasks to edge or near-user nodes, which shortens the data transmission path and minimizes processing delays. Additionally, energy efficiency improves as devices and network nodes share computational loads, preventing energy-intensive operations from being concentrated in core servers. Offloading also enhances network scalability by reducing bottlenecks at centralized data centers, allowing the network to accommodate more users and services. Lastly, security and privacy are strengthened as distributed processing reduces the need for data to travel back to centralized locations, minimizing exposure risks during transmission and enabling sensitive information to be processed locally, which is particularly important for privacy-sensitive applications.

D. Payload Mobility

6G services will be composed of several administrative domains over different types of platforms. Essentially motivated by both financial and Service Level Agreement (SLA) compliance (i.e., reaching SLA at minimal costs), payload mobility and placement shall, in the first place, be friction-free

Fig. 1. NAFOMO overlay for orchestration and management of secure complex services.

during service deployment. This can be attained with platform-independent packaging (e.g., containers). In practice, friction-free migration is highly penalized by security enforcement and enablers. Secure payload migration does not come easily with the state of the art (e.g., due to enclave vendor lock-ins). The ultimate strategy to facilitate payload migration is the avoidance of any security dependencies, being hardware or kernel based. This comes with self-protected payloads where secure execution does not depend on the targeted hosts. In that regard, three forms of payloads, namely, binary, WebAssembly (WASM), and containerized, should be supported with self-contained security. By doing so, NAFOMO will contribute to WASM payload security, offering the first integrity verification. 6G networks will also benefit from blockchain-based and SECaaS-based mutual remote attestation schemes, which advance the domain of remote attestation, permitting any payload to control another payload while conferring a very elevated security level.

E. Disaggregated CRAN

Having a cloud-native and service-based architecture, 6G will take advantage of the multiple benefits provided by an application container orchestrator like Kubernetes, such as the management and monitoring of resources and dynamic scaling of the 6G Virtual Network Functions (VNFs). In the same vein, the containerized RAN follows a disaggregated architecture, including the Central, Distributed & Radio Units (CU, DU, and RU) components. This distributed scheme implements the functional split of the base station following the 3GPP split 7.2 specifications [11]. Specifically, the split takes place in the layer 2 OSI stack, between the Packet Data Convergence Protocol (PDCP) and Radio Link Control (RLC) layers. The DU integrates the lower layers (from the RLC and below), while the CU integrates the upper layers. The F1 interface is utilized for the communication between CU and DU and is based on the F1 Application. A key benefit of splitting the

RAN is that it allows for the reduction of features that need to be handled by the RU, enabling their implementation in a centralized DU instead. Furthermore, this split enables the placement of the RAN components (e.g., CU and DU) in the cloud or in the edge, whereas the RU is located alongside the commercial/SDR remote RU. These capabilities are crucial for any resource-efficient and flexible orchestration scheme in 6G.

III. NETWORK FOOTPRINT-OPTIMIZED MANAGEMENT AND ORCHESTRATION (NAFOMO)

The NAFOMO orchestration and management framework will be built on four pillars, which are described below and depicted in Figure 1 with its components.

A. Federated slice orchestration and management

This pillar entails federated solutions for secure-by-design orchestration and management of 6G cloud-native slices, transcending access-to-core and edge-to-cloud domains. The security-by-design approach will be facilitated through the optimal translation of end-to-end security intents of slices, with AI assistance where applicable, and their deployment across domains involved in hosting a 6G slice. Overall, the NATWORK project promotes security-by-design and energy sustainability as strongly intertwined targets in the management and orchestration (MANO) solution it is developing. This is driven by the large cloudification of 6G services, which has advantages in the flexible scaling of 6G provisions. On the other hand, it increases the risk of Denial of Sustainability - typically observed in the cloud - against 6G services and/or the infrastructure hosting them. NAFOMO intrinsically adopts the cloud-native paradigm in 6G, supporting containerized network functions and adopting the microservices architecture in constructing cloud-native 6G slices through inter-microservice connectivity. Moreover, the NAFOMO will feature federated

orchestration across multiple domains, thereby offering end-to-end scheduling and security management over the lifecycle of a 6G slice.

As key optimality objectives, NAFOMO intends to tackle the energy efficiency/greenness of a slice, a cross-cutting target across all domains, and the trade-offs posed with security and performance. To this end, while a range of design choices will be explored for these solutions, particular focus is on decentralized federation approaches that allow involved actor(s) - e.g., autonomous domains of compute and network orchestrators - the ability to interact to construct and connect multiple segments that ultimately provide the secured end-to-end slice. NETWORK envisions a scalable through federation end-to-end service orchestration platform built as a highly distributed grid of domain-level orchestrators, spread across multiple geo-dispersed and potentially heterogeneous edge environments. Federation between domain-level orchestrators ensures end-to-end principles over the edge-to-cloud continuum. Security by design in the orchestrators' domain will essentially preserve threat identification and isolation. The approach is aimed at enabling security by flexible and scalable solutions.

B. Data plane computation optimization

This pillar is a novel approach to offloading specific security services, micro-services, and network functions as purely data plane programmable pipelines within 6G networks. The decentralized feature extraction (DFE) architecture for AI-based algorithms, developed under the NETWORK framework, targets enhancing 6G security at the device level. The proposed DFE design is conceived for AI-driven techniques such as traffic pattern prediction, anomaly detection, Federated Learning mitigation, and AI-as-a-Service for cybersecurity (AIaaSes), and relies on programmable packet processing and manipulation [12]. These mechanisms will strengthen the security posture of 6G networks by processing telemetry data and aggregating features in a distributed manner. A key advantage of this decentralized approach is its ability to maintain data privacy. Instead of sharing entire datasets, only the extracted features are transmitted to the AI layer, thereby minimizing the volume of data exchanged between 6G data plane elements (switches, smart NICs, DPUs, 6G whiteboxes, and pure data plane VNF containers) and analytics collectors. This approach significantly reduces latency, enabling real-time detection and mitigation of network threats.

Additionally, the pillar envisions the design and pipeline mapping of Wirespeed AI (WAI) models to ensure early detection of attacks, including Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) and Advanced Persistent Threats (APTs) [13]. Various AI methods are explored, ranging from simple models to more resource-intensive approaches such as Decision Trees, Linear SVM, Logistic Regression, Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) for time-series forecasting, and Reinforcement Learning (RL). The DFE and WAI methods are deployed across multiple segments of the 6G network, including core, edge, and RAN.

Different offloading strategies based on device acceleration features are under evaluation, such as programmable ASICs,

CPUs, GPUs, FPGAs, DPUs, virtual bypass mechanisms, and novel hybrid backends, such as DPU with embedded GPU [14]. By analyzing the computational capabilities of each 6G data plane element, optimal WAI offloading strategies will be implemented and enforced to ensure the efficient placement of decentralized security functions across the network in NAFOMO. Instead of executing big monolithic AI/ML models on centralized devices, AI slicing will improve computational efficiency within 6G networks by disaggregating a large model into several smaller, lightweight components.

AI slicing allows for more dynamic scaling and easier model reconfiguration, enabling the network to adapt to fluctuating traffic loads and resource availability without overburdening central processing units. By distributing the AI workload across multiple data plane components, the overall resource usage and energy efficiency can be optimized, reducing the strain on any single network element. This approach aligns with the broader goals of 6G to provide sustainable, high-performance network services.

C. Intent-based service security and associated adaptive placement of security and services

This pillar focuses on providing optimal distribution of in-network 6G security services within the edge-to-cloud continuum in such a manner that secure-by-design principles are achieved while preserving the sustainability goal. In order to realize our objective, a composition overlay of microservices and optimization algorithms, tackling the trade-off between security and energy consumption, will be utilized on various components of the 6G architecture. In addition, by leveraging virtualization technologies such as VNFs and Containerised Network Functions (CNFs), dynamic adjustment of intent-based security services will be enabled, allowing continuous security provisioning across the network. Intent-based security involves defining and enforcing security policies based on high-level intents expressed by users or network operators. This requires addressing several challenges, such as managing the dynamicity, providing contextual awareness, dealing with heterogeneous edge-cloud-IoT continuum and multi-tenancy, natural language processing, etc. Leveraging AI/ML models is needed to automatically translate high-level security intents into actionable, dynamic policies that adapt to real-time threats and network conditions, but also for managing the mitigation and prevention strategies. One strong candidate for the foundation of this pillar is the concept of MTD [15]. The envisaged idea is to exploit payload mobility as an MTD action type and develop AI-based policies for providing an optimized and automated MTD mechanism. By following this approach in a complex 6G environment with multiple network domains and various microservices, an optimal operating point on the scale of MTD overhead against security gain can be achieved. Moreover, in order to justify the actions taken by the MTD mechanism, as well as to increase the robustness of our solution, explainability techniques will be incorporated into NAFOMO, allowing security experts to gain insights from AI-powered decisions.

TABLE I
KPIs AND IMPROVEMENTS W.R.T. SOTA TARGETED IN NAFOMO

KPI	Description	Related UC	Improvement
KPI 1	Quantifies the system's ability to maintain service continuity and performance by minimizing latency disruptions. In scenarios involving DoSt attacks, the orchestration layer is designed to ensure efficient service recovery and the re-establishment of connections in alignment with the intended service objectives, targeting a 10% improvement.	UC 1	10%
KPI 2	Measures the reduction of unnecessary energy consumption within the orchestrated system. The deployment of sustainable, energy-aware mechanisms across the continuum will minimize energy waste during operation, with a targeted improvement of 10%.	UC 1	10%
KPI 3	Tracks the efficiency of x86 native applications, specifically regarding their start-up time and operational performance under security-driven conditions. The goal is to maintain minimal degradation in both performance and energy consumption, even when stringent security measures are applied, with targeted thresholds of less than one second startup time, less than 10% performance degradation during runtime, and less than 10% energy waste.	UC 2	<1 sec, <10%, <10%
KPI 4	Ensures that security mechanisms applied to WASM payloads are equivalent to those used for x86 native implementations, thereby supporting the creation of secure and efficient platform-independent systems.	UC 2	-

Furthermore, federated learning will be leveraged with a primary focus on energy efficiency, in a privacy-preserving manner. Federated learning reduces the need to transmit large volumes of data by securely aggregating the model parameters [16]. Additionally, privacy-preserving approaches utilizing cryptographic techniques ensure the confidentiality and integrity of the transmitted data throughout the federated learning process, and trust management approaches ensure that only reliable and authenticated entities participate in the system. Combining all these components, NAFOMO aims to operate in a secure closed-loop configuration where no action by a human is necessary, in compliance with the ETSI ZSM paradigm.

D. Enhanced payload mobility with migratable security methods

This pillar is focused on elaborating sustainable security and fostering platform-agnostic and performance-acceptable security. It will focus on the packaging of binary, containerized, and WASM payloads. For each packaging, NAFOMO will exploit WASM payload runtime verification, always-sustainable binary code integrity verification, and mutual remote attestation leveraging blockchain. It will consider the real impact on friction to deployment, security, performance, and sustainability of trusted execution, notably when used for placement of security service.

IV. RELEVANT USE CASES FOR THE NAFOMO

To have a concrete description of our work, we will employ two UCs in our implementation and subsequent evaluations. As 6G networks become more pervasive, they will require increasing amounts of energy to power the massive number of connected devices and data-intensive applications. With energy consumption being a critical factor in the sustainability and cost-effectiveness of 6G networks, these use cases will explore innovative energy solutions that can support reliable connectivity and high-quality services while reducing energy costs and minimizing environmental impact in an orchestration and management framework over the 6G continuum.

A. UC 1 - Decentralised management and orchestration service for intent-compliant end-to-end service resiliency and continuity

This use-case focuses on demonstrating NETWORK's MANO service that enables communication and coordination across multiple infrastructure components and service providers in response to cascade denial of sustainability (DoSt) attacks. The coordination will result in re-optimization: placement, reachability/routing, and scale of services in compliance with end-to-end service intents, including the fraction of demand executed using green/renewable energy. The essential version of the demonstration will incorporate at least one optimization algorithm in the orchestration service, involving an edge-to-cloud computing continuum connected by a programmable network.

B. UC 2 - SECaaS for the pre-deployment of dependable software generation

This use case pertains to the enhancement of trustworthiness levels for software payloads and processed data, dynamically deployed and instantiated across the edge-to-cloud continuum. The focus is on a) security-sensitive network monitoring functions and edge processing and b) WASM payloads. The core aspect of the demonstration will involve simulating various attack types, such as vulnerability searches, tampering, cloning, node impersonation, and DoS attacks targeting the platform.

C. Use Case KPIs and Expected Outcomes

The evaluation of the NAFOMO orchestration framework is based on specific key performance indicators (KPIs) that measure the system's capabilities in energy efficiency, security, and overall system reliability in 6G network environments. These KPIs and their envisaged improvement with respect to SoTA are summarized in Table I.

The expected outcomes from the evaluation of the UCs are:

- **Dynamic Slice Migration:** In response to DoSt attacks, the framework will showcase its capability to migrate slices seamlessly while maintaining service availability and security across the edge-to-cloud continuum.

Fig. 2. Mapping of KPIs and outcomes to UCs.

- **Runtime-aware Workload Orchestration:** The system dynamically adjusts workloads based on real-time security and energy metrics. By continuously monitoring network conditions, it optimizes resource allocation, balancing performance, security, and energy efficiency. The system adapts to changes in network demand, ensuring seamless operation across edge and cloud environments while minimizing energy consumption.
- **Platform-independent Software Security:** The development of security mechanisms for x86-compiled payloads that are both sustainable and platform-agnostic.
- **Enhanced Security for WASM Payloads:** This outcome focuses on applying a robust security framework for WASM payloads, particularly in edge computing environments.

Figure 2 visualizes the mapping of outcomes to UCs. For UC 1, KPI 1 ensures that the decentralized system adapts to latency requirements dynamically, leading to Dynamic Slice Migration, which is key for maintaining service continuity. As for KPI 2, it drives Energy Waste Reduction, which optimizes real-time energy use, combined with the workload orchestration process. For UC 2, KPI 3 ensures that native x86 software and services are optimized for security and performance, leading to Platform-Independent Software Security, while KPI 4 focuses on reinforcing security measures specific to WASM Payloads, improving their resilience against potential threats.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presents the NAFOMO security orchestration and management framework currently being developed in the NETWORK project. This architecture is driven by bio-inspired and energy efficiency paradigms and relies on different security enablers. We also describe two selected use cases for secure complex services.

One of the key research directions for the framework is the development of novel optimization schemes that are applicable to different scenarios and network domains over the 6G continuum. Moreover, these enablers should be supported via relevant monitoring and data aggregation infrastructure. That aspect requires the development of open and well-designed APIs between the NAFOMO components. The optimized integration of data plane techniques with a ubiquitous orchestration substrate is another challenge since the envisaged framework is supposed to utilize different network layers for footprint-optimized and efficient security orchestration.

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